

An Alternative approach to IBFS for Transportation Problem

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Abstract

In this paper, we suggested the median method to find the IBFS of transportation problem (TP) where the difference among per unit transportation cost (TC) in each row & columns are more. The Arithmetic mean method (AMM) & its constraints are already discussed to solve such type of TP. We have shown how the IBFS is calculated using NWCR, LCM, VAM, AMM, and our proposed method. The proposed method gets the best results with the least amount of time and effort in such a type of TP. Our paper uses a real life problem to show how the method works. Through a comparative study, we got how well the proposed method works and found that it is easier to compute and gives similar results as AMM methods. The proposed method is also easier to compute than AMM if the number of origins & destinations is more.

Keywords: IBFS, TP, TC, VAM, AMM, LCM, NWCR, Median method.

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Introduction

Since the company spends millions of dollars carrying items from supply to demand, transportation expenses are a crucial factor for many businesses [7]. The conventional transportation issue, which aims to minimize the cost of transporting varied quantities of a single homogeneous item from multiple origins to different destinations, is a prominent and significant kind of linear programming problem [1]. The challenge is to identify a workable "shipping pattern" between sources and destinations that minimizes the overall transportation costs [5]. The transportation problem specifies the quantity of consignments to be delivered from various sources to various destinations such that the overall transportation cost is minimized without breaking the availability and demand constraints [3]. A transportation problem (TP) is a unique mathematical programming problem that plays an essential role in shipping products or services from several supply sources to multiple demand destinations. The oldest TP was presented by (Hitchcock, 1941), which may be characterized as Linear Programming Problems (LPP) in which the objective function and demand and supply constraints are linear. Transportation, as it pertains to physical distribution, is solely concerned with freight services. As a result of industry deregulation, freight transportation in the United States has seen significant changes [2]. There is an easy method to calculate an IBFS for a transportation problem. At this level, the approach is worthy of study since it presents the computational process that serves as the basis for the general solution methodology based on the simplex method [6].

Business logistics includes transportation as one of its primary duties. A warehouse cannot work without transportation, despite the fact that storage is perhaps the most important logistical factor [4]. The primary stage in solving a TP is to identify an IBFS, which is further refined until it is optimal. IBFS plays an essential part in TP, and several ways to get this solution have been explored in the past, such as the North-West corner rule, Vogel's approximation approach, Least Cost method, etc [7]. When the greatest cost spans two or more columns or rows, the VAM Method cannot provide a reasonable answer [8].

A comparative study of VAM & AMM (Arithmetic Mean Method) through a numerical problem was given by [9], and they said that in some problems, AMM is more suitable than VAM method for finding IBFS; they also confessed that the computation by this method is very tedious if the number of origins and destinations are large in size. We have introduced a new technique called Median Method, which is easy to calculate, and the IBFS is the same as in AMM in the TP where the difference among per unit transportation costing each row & column is more. The median method's advantage is saving time when the sources and destination are larger in number. One of the most important parts of business supply chain management is transportation. Even though warehousing is probably the most important part of logistics, a warehouse can't do its job without transportation [4].

Mathematical Formulation of Transportation Problems

Transportation models figure out how to get a product made in different plants or factories (called "sources of supply") to several warehouses. The aim is to meet the needs of the warehouses within the plant's capacity and with the lowest possible transport costs. Consequently, transportation models are commonly utilized when commodities must be transported from manufacturers to depots, from depots to wholesalers, from dealers to shops, and

from shops to buyers. To solve transportation models, you must determine how many units should be carried from each supply source to each demand point to satisfy all of the demand sites' demands while minimizing overall transportation costs.

Consider of the m-plant sources as O1, O2, and Om, and the retail market destinations as D1, D2, and Dn. Assuming that ai > 0 is true for all plants, let Oi = 1, 2,..., m represent the amount at the ith plant. Let bj > 0, where j = 1, 2,..., n, be the price being sought after at the jth spot in the market.

Let Cij represent the price of transporting one unit from its origin to its jth destination if I = 1, 2,..., m and j = 1, 2,..., n. If Xij ≥ 0 is the amount that needs to be transported from the ith origin to the jth destination, the goal is to choose Xij in such a way that the entire cost of transporting it

$$Min Z = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n x_{ij} C_{ij}$$

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is as low as possible. $Z. \sum_{j=1}^n x_{ij} = a_i \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m$

$$\sum_{i=1}^m x_{ij} = b_j \quad j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$$

& all $x_{ij} \geq 0 \quad \forall i \& j$

Origin/Destinations	D1	D2	D3		Dn	Supply
O1	C11(x11)	C12	C13		C1n	a1
O2	C21	C22	C33		C2n	a2
..						
Om	Cm1	Cm2	Cm3		Cmn	am
Demand	b1	b2	b3		bn	

Assumptions in Transportation Problems

One of the most important rules is that the cost of sending commodities from source i to destination j depends directly on the quantity of products conveyed.

Also, a transportation model is said to be balanced if demand and supply are the same. In a balanced situation, everything that can be offered is used to meet demand. Since there are no gaps, all limits are the same, not different. Even so, a transportation model is out of balance when demand is higher than supply. To get an IBFS, you must fix the problem of the unbalanced problem by The creation of a fictitious origin or a dummy market, depending on the demand and supply conditions.

Network diagram of Transportation Problem

Algorithm for the proposed method

The proposed median method is a heuristic approach used to find an initial basic feasible solution for transportation problems. Here are the algorithm steps for the median method:

Step1: find out the transportation cost matrix for each source and destination pair.

Step 2: Determine the totals for each source and destination's rows and columns.

Step 3: For the matrix of transportation costs, compute the row and column medians.

Step 4: Find the cell with the highest median value in step four.

Step 5: Distribute as much of the available supply as you can between the highest-median row and the highest-median column.

Step 6: Update the row and column totals as necessary in step six.

Step 7: Deleting the fully allotted row or column.

Step 8: Continue with steps 3 through 7 until no more rows or columns remain.

Step 9: Assign as much as you can to the cells with the greatest medians in the remaining rows or columns, choosing the one with the highest total.

Step 10: Update the totals for the assigned rows and columns and delete them.

Step 11: Continue with steps 3 through 10 until no more rows or columns remain.

Step 12: Distribute the remaining supply to the cells with the highest medians if any unallocated cells are still available.

Step 13: Determine if the supply and demand limitations are met by comparing the row and column totals to the solution.

Step 14: Implement an improvement step (such as the stepping-stone approach) if the proposed solution is not feasible.

Step 15: The algorithm ends and the initial basic feasible solution is obtained if the solution is feasible. Real-Life Transportation Problem

A transporter collects the number of units of goods from numbers of origins (sources) i.e., O_1 , O_2 , and O_3 are 12, 7, 5, respectively, and distributed on different destinations (locations) D_1 , D_2 , D_3 , D_4 unit wise, which are 5, 4, 4, 11, 24. To obtain IBFS of TP

Table: 1 (IBFS by Median Method)

	D₁	D₂	D₃	D₄	a_i
O₁	95(5)	105(4)	80	15(3)	12
O₂	115	180	40(4)	30 (3)	7
O₃	155	180	95	70(5)	5
b_j	5	4	4	11	24

IBFS of TP. $Z = 95 \times 5 + 105 \times 4 + 15 \times 3 + 40 \times 4 + 30 \times 3 + 70 \times 5 = 1540$

Table: 2 (IBFS by Arithmetic Mean Method)

	D₁	D₂	D₃	D₄	a_i
O₁	95(5)	105(4)	80	15(3)	12
O₂	115	180	40(4)	30 (3)	7
O₃	155	180	95	70(5)	5
b_j	5	4	4	11	24

IBFS of TP. $Z = 95 \times 5 + 105 \times 4 + 15 \times 3 + 40 \times 4 + 30 \times 3 + 70 \times 5 = 1540$

Table:3 (IBFS by VAM)

	D₁	D₂	D₃	D₄	a_i
O₁	95	105(4)	80	15(8)	12

O₂	115 (3)	180	40 (4)	30	7
O₃	155 (2)	180	95	70 (3)	5
b_j	5	4	4	11	24

IBFS of TP. $Z = 105x4 + 15x8 + 115x3 + 40x4 + 30x3 + 155x2 + 70x3 = 1565$

Table: 4 (IBFS by NWCR)

	D₁	D₂	D₃	D₄	a_i
O₁	95 (5)	105 (4)	80 (2)	15	12
O₂	115	180	40 (4)	30 (6)	7
O₃	155	180	95	70 (5)	5
b_j	5	4	4	11	24

IBFS of TP. $Z = 95x5 + 105x8 + 80x2 + 40x4 + 30x6 + 70x5 = 1705$

Table: 5 (IBFS by LCM)

	D₁	D₂	D₃	D₄	a_i
O₁	95 (1)	105	80	15 (11)	12
O₂	115 (3)	180	40 (4)	30	7
O₃	155 (1)	180 (4)	95	70	5
b_j	5	4	4	11	24

IBFS of TP. $Z = 95x1 + 15x11 + 115x3 + 40x4 + 155x1 + 180x4 = 1640$

Comparative study of above methods

(Graph -1)

(Graph -2)

Results & Discussion

In the discipline of operation research, the transportation problem (TP) is a well-known issue. There are two primary components to the solution. The best solution is reached after obtaining the Initial Basic Feasible Solution (IBFS). Finding IBFS of TP is frequently done using the North West Corner Method (NWCN), the Least Cost Method (LCM), the Arithmetic Mean Method (AMM), and Vogel's Approximation Method (VAM). We switch to the median technique to get the

IBFS of TP, where there is a larger difference between the per-unit transportation cost in each row and column.

We concluded from graphs 1 and 2 that the median technique, that's similar to the AMM method to produce IBFS of such type of TP where Vogel's method does not give the logical solution (where the difference between per unit transportation cost in each rows & columns are larger), But wherever there are more sources (origins) and destinations, computing the median approach is quite simple. The IBFS using this type of TP's , median technique provides results are closer to the optimal solution.

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